

“Why Do They Cheat?” Insights From University Students in Cambodia

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Abstract

Academic cheating has become a significant issue within higher education globally and the causes are typically bound to different social contexts. Unfortunately, empirical evidence on such deviant behaviors in the Asian context, especially in Cambodia, seems to be underrepresented in the literature. In this regard, the current study examines the common factors influencing academic cheating among students at universities in Phnom Penh, focusing on personal, school, social, and technological factors. This research employed a quantitative approach and collected data from 220 students from some universities and across various disciplines. The results of the study indicated that personal and school factors appear to have a significant influence on academic cheating among university students in Cambodia. In addition, social factors, peer pressure, parental expectations, and technological factors, also contribute to such deviant behaviors. This research, therefore, provides some policy implications, including enforcement of policies, perceptions of cheating, promotion of a culture of academic integrity, and digital literacy, which educational institutions need to incorporate and implement to reduce academic cheating.

Keywords: Academic cheating, personal factors, school factors, social factors, technological factors, Cambodia.

INTRODUCTION

Academic integrity refers to morals established to advance credibility, sincerity, responsibility, ethics, and intellectual growth in higher education (Henning et al., 2013; Park et al., 2014). Oppositely, academic cheating is often considered to involve engaging in illegal activities as a quick means of achieving success in the academic journey. It may include cheating in examinations and copying from others' homework, projects, or assignments (Hadjar, 2019). Meanwhile, the possibility of academic cheating, known as “e-cheating”, has significantly expanded due to integrating technological advancements into the classrooms and implementing online learning (King & Case, 2014). A study by Putarek and Pavlin-Bernardic (2019) stated that active and second-party cheating are the two elements of academic cheating. Cheating with the intention of attaining one's own favorable outcome is referred to as active cheating (e.g., copying test answers from other students) while cheating to assist others is defined as second-party cheating (e.g., allowing other students to copy homework or exams or assisting another student in sitting an exam).

Poor academic integrity, that is, academic cheating, has been a major challenge in educational institutions (Ashworth et al., 1997; Hadjar, 2019; Miller, Shoptaugh, & Wooldridge, 2011; Rettinger & Kramer, 2009). A lot of research has been carried out to discover the prevalence of academic cheating as well as its motivators (McCabe, Trevino, & Butterfield, 1997, 1999, 2001; Whitely, 1998). Previous studies have highlighted that the high rates of college students' cheating have prompted administrators to implement policies or honor codes to solve certain traits of cheaters. However, there seems to be a gap between the understanding of cheating rates and cheater characteristics and actions taken by institutions to diminish academic cheating. To reduce this kind of divide, over the past years, there has been a focus on the driving factors that influence and perpetuate students' cheating and how educational institutions can mitigate those factors (Jordan, 2001). Thus, this emphasizes that cheating is motivated by the relationships between personal factors and institutional contexts (McCabe & Trevino, 1997; Whitley, 1998). For instance, individual traits like age, gender, personality, ability, and extracurricular engagement, as well as contextual causes, including honor codes, penalties, and the likelihood of being caught, have been proven to be associated with academic cheating (e.g.

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Table 1. Demographics of the Participants (n=220)

Category	Subcategory	Percentage
Gender	Female	60.5%
	Male	36.4%
	Prefer not to say	3.2%
Age	Under 18	0.5%
	18-20	35.9%
	21-24	61.8%
	25-30	1.8%
Academic Level	Freshman	6.4%
	Sophomore	14.1%
	Junior	45.5%
	Senior	34.1%
Study Shift	Morning	49.5%
	Afternoon	10.5%
	Evening	40%
Field of Study	Language and Education	32.3%
	Management, Economics, Accounting, Finance, Business	29.7%
	Civil Engineering and Architecture	9.5%
	Law, Public Administration, International Relations	9.1%
	Computer Science and Technology	7.7%
	General Medicine and Nursing	5.5%
	Natural and Physical Sciences	4.8%
Other Study Areas	1.4%	
Academic Achievement	Excellent	8.2%
	Good	55.5%
	Average	34.1%
	Below Average	2.3%
Employment Status	Employed	50.5%
	Not Employed	49.5%
Employment Type	Full-time	26.4%
	Part-time	23.6%
	Self-employed	2.3%
	Not looking for jobs	32.3%
	Unemployed but actively searching	13.6%
	Others	1.8%

McCabe & Trevino, 1997; Murdock & Anderman, 2006; Rettinger & Kramer, 2009; Whitley, 1998).

Conceptualizing academic cheating pertaining to personal and contextual relationships, we have noticed that previous studies on this area have mainly been undertaken in Europe and North America, which are developed nations. Those studies have found that a large proportion of college students are involved in some certain sorts of cheating activities (Teixeira & Rocha, 2010; Zhao et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2024). While a lot of research has been done in the Western context, there remains doubt about the applicability of these findings in the Asian context. In Cambodia, academic cheating poses a particularly urgent challenge due to the country's rapid expansion in higher education institutions, the increase in student enrollment, and the integration of digital platforms in education (Ban & Heng, 2023; Roe et al., 2024; Sok & Heng, 2024). Despite these shifts, there is limited national policy toward academic dishonesty, and institutional responses remain fragmented or inconsistently enforced (Heng, 2024). At the same time, empirical evidence on the recent development of cheating behaviors is scarce. This

lack of evidence prevents policymakers and educators from designing effective and evidence-based interventions to promote academic integrity in Cambodian universities (Maeda, 2021, Roe et al., 2024). This lack of data in various higher education settings hinders our understanding of academic integrity, as well as preventing us from developing stronger policies to deal with this conundrum in different higher education contexts. Therefore, this present study aims to investigate the common factors that are attributed to academic cheating among students at universities in Cambodia.

Literature Review

Definition of academic cheating

Academic cheating is defined by many researchers. “Academic cheating”, “academic dishonesty”, and “academic misconduct” are replaceable when referring to an academic integrity contravention even though “misconduct” and “cheating” are used to describe actions, yet “dishonesty” refers to an abstract idea (Park, Park, & Jang, 2013). “Academic cheating” is

Table 2. Students' Engagement in Academic Cheating (n=220)

Items	Values	Gender		Employment	
		M	F	Employed	Unemployed
1. How often do you hear about academic cheating among your peers?	Never	18.75	8.27	17.39	6.67
	Rarely	21.25	21.80	19.13	22.86
	Occasionally	37.50	38.30	40.00	37.14
	Frequently	16.25	21.80	13.91	24.76
	Very Frequently	6.25	9.77	9.57	8.57
2. Do you believe that cheating is common among your peers?	Never	16.25	12.03	14.78	12.38
	Rarely	21.25	26.32	27.83	19.05
	Occasionally	40.00	36.84	33.91	42.86
	Frequently	17.50	15.04	14.78	19.05
	Very Frequently	5.00	9.77	8.70	6.67
3. Have you ever engaged in academic cheating during your time at university?	Never	28.75	25.56	30.40	22.90
	Rarely	31.25	41.35	36.52	37.14
	Occasionally	31.25	23.31	26.09	25.71
	Frequently	3.75	5.26	4.35	7.62
	Very Frequently	5.00	4.51	2.61	6.67

defined as “any intentional action or behavior that violates the established rules governing the completion of a test or assignment, gives one student an unfair advantage over other students on a test or assignment, or decreases the accuracy of the intended inferences arising from a student’s performance on a test or an assignment” (Cizek, 2004, p. 308). Similarly, according to Park, Park and Jang (2013), unethical or

unauthorized behavior that violates academic integrity is considered as “academic cheating.” Anitha and Sundaram (2021) define cheating as trying to carry out tasks without abiding by the principle of honesty. When observed within the academic field, it is called academic dishonesty, indicating unethical practices within an educational environment.

Table 3. Personal Factors Influencing Academic Cheating (n=220)

Items	Values	Gender		Employment	
		M	F	Employed	Unemployed
1. Do you cheat because you do not trust their own answers?	Undecided	15.00	13.50	15.65	12.38
	Disagree	43.75	45.86	47.83	40.00
	Agree	41.25	40.60	36.52	47.62
2. Do you cheat because you have less skill level in a particular course?	Undecided	7.50	11.28	13.04	5.71
	Disagree	45.00	48.12	44.35	47.62
	Agree	47.50	40.60	42.61	46.67
3. Do you cheat because you do not understand lessons well?	Undecided	5.00	10.53	9.57	7.62
	Disagree	42.50	36.84	39.13	38.10
	Agree	52.50	52.63	51.30	54.29
4. Do you cheat because you engage in extracurricular activities cheat and do not have time to review lessons?	Undecided	10.00	14.29	12.17	14.29
	Disagree	47.50	39.10	40.87	42.86
	Agree	42.50	46.67	46.96	42.86
5. Do you cheat because you excuse their actions as a result of teachers' faults?	Undecided	16.25	17.29	17.39	16.19
	Disagree	60.00	65.41	60.00	66.67
	Agree	23.75	17.29	22.61	17.14
6. Do you cheat because you are afraid of failing your exams?	Undecided	6.30	8.30	11.30	2.86
	Disagree	33.75	32.33	33.04	33.33
	Agree	60.00	59.40	55.65	63.81
7. Do you cheat because you want to get high scores?	Undecided	10.00	13.53	14.78	10.48
	Disagree	57.50	52.63	50.43	58.10
	Agree	32.50	33.83	34.78	31.43
8. Do you cheat because you are out of time?	Undecided	8.75	10.53	10.43	9.52
	Disagree	37.50	44.36	38.26	44.76
	Agree	53.75	45.11	51.30	45.71

Table 4. School Factors Influencing Academic Cheating (n=220)

Items	Values	Gender		Employment	
		M	F	Employed	Unemployed
9. Do you cheat because you are less likely to be caught by your teachers during exams?	Undecided	12.50	16.54	14.78	18.10
	Disagree	51.25	53.38	49.57	55.24
	Agree	36.25	30.08	35.65	26.67
10. Do you cheat due to larger class sizes where there is little interaction with your teachers?	Undecided	12.50	18.05	19.13	13.33
	Disagree	50.00	57.14	52.17	58.10
	Agree	37.50	24.81	28.70	28.57
11. Do you feel pressured to cheat because exam papers are very difficult?	Undecided	13.80	12.00	14.78	9.52
	Disagree	40.00	34.59	35.65	36.19
	Agree	46.25	53.38	49.57	54.29
12. Do you feel pressured to cheat because schools prioritize grades over actual learning?	Undecided	5.00	14.29	13.91	6.67
	Disagree	51.25	47.37	46.09	53.33
	Agree	43.75	38.35	40.00	40.00

Prevalence of academic cheating in university setting

Academic cheating seems to be common on college campuses around the world for both objective and subjective causes, including students' copying assignments from others, plagiarism, use of crib notes or cheat notes during a test or examination (Ma, McCabe, & Liu, 2013). Estimates regarding the frequency of college students' academic cheating differ partly due to researchers concentrating on different forms of academic cheating and using various methodologies to assess it (Jensen, et al., 2002). However, Whitley's (1998) findings of college students' cheating showed that 40.9% of students cheated on homework, 47% of students had engaged in plagiarism, 43.1% had cheated on examinations, and the percentage of students admitted having cheated at least one form of academic activity is 70.4%. Another study (Anitha & Sundaram, 2021) found that the majority of students engage in academically dishonest behaviors, including seeking outside help (76.4%), plagiarism (72.6%), using online information without proper citation, and submitting copied assignments or unoriginal work (65.1%), lying about academic assignments (50.9%), and cheating in exams (over 50%). Therefore, the commonness of college students' dishonest practices in academic study is a concerning and pervasive issue that has been given much attention in both research and academic debates. Across the broader Southeast Asian region, academic dishonesty continues to be an issue. A study on nursing students in a Southeast Asian country reported that 44.1% engaged in at least one type of academic dishonesty and many in multiple forms (Bloomfield, Crawford, & Fisher, 2021). Similarly, research in Malaysia showed plagiarism and the misuse of digital resources as prevalent forms of academic misconduct among higher education students (Mustapha et al., 2017). Specifically in Cambodia, Maeda (2021) found that cheating was common and influenced by peer behavior, institutional policy, and teacher-student relationships.

Factors influencing academic cheating among university students

Studies consistently reveal a variety of factors contributing to university students' academic dishonesty, especially in terms of personal and contextual factors (Whitley, 1998; Shmeleva &

Semenova, 2018; Rettinger & Kramer, 2008; McCabe & Trevino, 1997). For this literature review, factors have been sorted into four major categories: personal factors, school factors, social factors, and technological factors.

Personal factors

Personal factors play a vital role in contributing to students' academic cheating. Students' fear of performing poorly or students who are less skilled in a particular course are more likely to cheat (Whitley, 1998). A study by Yu et al. (2016) indicated that academic cheating is driven by a lack of self-control. The study also indicated that students who have a strong sense of others-centeredness in their lives are less likely to cheat while students who have a strong sense of self-centeredness in their lives are more likely to cheat. Moreover, students' involvement in extracurricular activities leads them to cheat as they reflect on the time requirements that these extracurricular activities affect them and their choice to use various “shortcuts” to remain current and competitive in their schoolwork (McCabe & Trevino, 1997). In addition, when students can excuse their actions as the result of external factors, including teachers' faults or blaming cultures, they are prone to feel that their behavior is legitimate (Murdock & Stephens, 2007). Another study by McCabe, Trevino, and Butterfield (1999) found that students undertaking academic dishonesty were affected differently. The reasons for them could be the need to score higher points, high expectations from parents or relatives who put pressure on students to achieve really good results in their studies because this would help them to find a desired job later and build up their future career, and fear of doing something wrong as they usually lack adequate-proper work.

School factors

School factors also contribute to the establishment of an environment promoting academic dishonesty among university students. Students tend to cheat when they feel there is a lesser chance of being caught, especially in cases where their results on an important test are unsatisfactorily poor (Bushway, 1977). The author also mentioned that the level of availability and possible chances for cheating are among the most important

Table 5. Social Factors Influencing Academic Cheating (n=220)

Items	Values	Gender		Employment	
		M	F	Employed	Unemployed
13. Do you cheat because you learn this from their peers who engage in cheating?	Undecided	10.00	18.00	14.78	15.24
	Disagree	55.00	48.90	50.43	49.52
	Agree	35.00	33.08	34.80	35.20
14. Do you cheat because you feel pressured by your parents' expectations for good grades?	Undecided	8.75	18.05	17.39	11.43
	Disagree	56.25	54.14	49.57	60.00
	Agree	35.00	27.82	33.04	28.57
15. Do you cheat because you are influenced by social norms like "everyone is doing it."?	Undecided	10.00	16.54	16.52	12.38
	Disagree	51.25	51.88	46.96	56.19
	Agree	38.75	31.58	36.52	31.43

factors contributing to students' motivation towards engaging in dishonest behavior. Whitley (1998) implied that frequent large lecture classes with minimal interaction between teachers and students often create an environment of dislike based on which one may cheat without the likelihood of being caught or punished. Additionally, Anitha and Sundaram (2021) found out that conventional teaching methods and old or irrelevant course syllabi are the factors that contribute to reducing the interest of students in learning. Similarly, teachers who set overly hard tests or exams create the chance of cheating because students may feel despair or hopeless during these difficult assessments (Steininger, Johnson, & Kirts, 1964). Finally, it was found that the schools emphasizing performance goals concentrate their policies and practices more towards grades and personal capacities (Anderman, Griesinger, & Westfield, 1998). In such situations, students very often find the shortest way to accomplish their goals. On the contrary, if students consider their success in school to be dependent primarily on grades and abilities, then they are more liable to see cheating as an acceptable practice.

Social factors

Various social causes also affect academic misconduct. The behavior of peers influences students' violations against academic honesty because cheating is seen as approved; they use it to achieve and maintain success (McCabe & Trevino, 1997). The researchers claimed that people learn behaviors from others and deviant behavior is influenced by close contact with those engaged in misconduct. Seeing classmates' resort to cheating as a way of making success puts the chances high that people would use deceptive tactics, which are quite effective in setting one's behavior. Furthermore, academic dishonesty stems from social pressures as well as parental expectations and the need for affiliation without sincere interest (Anitha & Sundaram, 2021). This study showed that overparenting and high pressure for better grades among students could contribute to academically dishonest behavior. The authors stated that peer pressure and the fear of exclusion are also other factors that tend to force students into academic dishonesty so that they fit in well with their peers. Likewise, direct observation of others often causes sociability effects like following social norms. Cheating has an impact on students and can be seen from both positive and negative sides; however, its significance depends

upon the particulars of social standards relevant to a certain environment (Rettinger & Kramer, 2008). The study showed that cheating behavior is influenced by social context and taught norms. Signals contribute to cheating behavior even within student groups by neutralizing beliefs like "everyone else is doing it."

Technological factors

With the advent of technological breakthroughs, new elements for academically dishonest practices are posed in various ways. Misbehaviors related to misconduct have shifted from the old way of approaching these activities to advanced strategies via cheat sheets, unsanctioned discussions, falsified data or figures, using electronic devices in an examination, participating in unauthorized collaborative efforts, and infringing on others' exam papers without consent (Anitha & Sundaram, 2021). A study conducted in 2013 revealed that approximately 29% of online course attendees acknowledged cheating on exams about three and a half times per student (King & Case, 2014). The ever-increasing number of virtual classes poses an issue in unethical behavior. When making examinations online, students can even cheat by using illegitimate materials during closed-book assessments or by getting another classmate or friend to take the examination for them. According to the results obtained by Bain (2015), the Internet offers ample unrestricted opportunities in terms of accessibility for students who have basic knowledge about searching. Nowadays, the term "Google" refers to a search for information online. Since search results are digital, students can easily copy and paste information into their assignments. Some students who are good at the internet use digital tools that they find them not only for academic purposes but also for social networking reasons. For instance, recently, it has become an academic dishonesty tool like Facebook, which allows the exchange of materials such as exam questions (Bain, 2015).

METHOD

This research utilized a quantitative study (Kumar, 2014). This approach was more appropriate to investigate the extent of this issue on a large scale. Furthermore, it aligned with the research objective by offering a systematic, statistically supported

Table 6. Technological Factors Influencing Academic Cheating (n=220)

Items	Values	Gender		Employment	
		M	F	Employed	Unemployed
17. Do you cheat because you discuss with peers to share the answers using online devices, such as Google Meet, Zoom, or Discord??	Undecided	11.25	18.80	20.90	9.50
	Disagree	41.25	43.61	38.26	47.62
	Agree	47.50	37.59	40.87	42.86
18. Do you cheat because you use electronic devices to share answers through messaging apps like Messenger or Telegram?	Undecided	7.50	17.29	20.00	5.71
	Disagree	46.25	40.60	41.74	44.76
	Agree	46.25	42.11	38.26	49.52
19. Do you cheat because you use search engines like Google for answers during exams?	Undecided	6.25	13.53	12.17	9.52
	Disagree	50.00	42.11	46.96	41.90
	Agree	43.75	44.36	40.87	48.57
20. Do you cheat because you know the answers through social media platforms like Facebook, which is used inappropriately for sharing exam questions and answers?	Undecided	12.50	18.05	14.78	17.14
	Disagree	55.00	57.89	53.91	59.05
	Agree	32.50	24.06	31.30	23.81

investigation of the leading factors influencing academic cheating, and it allowed for a broader understanding of this phenomenon. This study adopted a cross-sectional design and collected data from respondents with various characteristics and backgrounds. To recruit participants, we employed convenience and snowball (networking) sampling methods (Kumar, 2014) and sent an online survey to various university students, requesting them to forward it to their networks. A total of 220 responses were received (see Table 1). However, it is essential to recognize that these sampling methods may lead to biased results and limit the generalizability of the findings to all university students.

The questionnaire was developed by the authors, based on literature review, and consists of three sections. Section I- Participants' background; Section II- Students' engagement in academic cheating; Section III - Main questions about factors influencing academic cheating among university students, including personal, social, school, and technological factors. A 5-point Likert scale (1 = Undecided, 2 = Strongly Disagree, 3 = Disagree, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree) was employed to measure participants' attitudes towards each factor. Overall, our research instrument consisted of 32 items, which underwent reviews by our academic supervisor. The data were analyzed in SPSS software. For the ease of data visualization, we also combined the positive and negative values into two categories: Agree and Disagree, and reported the data in percentages.

Table 1 presents the demographics of the 220 surveyed participants. Of these individuals, 60.5% were female. The age distribution was diverse, but the majority were between 18 and 20 (35.9%) and 21 to 24 (61.8%). Besides, the largest portion of the students were in their third year (45.5%), followed by those in their final year (34.1%). Half of the students (49.5%) were in morning classes, while 40% attended evening sessions. The surveyed respondents pursued various degrees across different universities in Phnom Penh, mainly in Language and Education (32.3%) and Business-related fields (29.7%). In terms of academic achievement, most students rated themselves as “Good” (55.5%), followed by “Average” (34.1%), and

“Excellent” (8.2%). Half of those students (50.5%) were employed; 26.4% were engaged in full-time positions and 23.6% worked part-time.

RESULTS

Students' engagement in academic cheating

Table 2 presents key insights into students' engagement and perceptions of academic cheating, categorized by gender and employment status. Approximately half of the students reported having heard about cheating, ranging from “occasionally” to “very frequently.” They also believed such behavior was typical among their peers. When asked about their own engagement in cheating, around 30% of the students acknowledged that they were occasionally engaged in some aspect of cheating. Similarly, between 30-40% of the participants were rarely involved in cheating, and a few admitted to (very) frequent cheating (10%). These results suggest that academic cheating is a relatively common behavior among students, with no notable variations observed across gender and employment status.

Factors influencing academic cheating

Personal factors

Table 3 suggests that students may have engaged in academic cheating due to exam pressure and a poor understanding of the lessons. Just over half of the participants identified the fear of failing exams and a poor understanding of the lessons as the most significant drivers, with no apparent difference in perception by gender or employment status. Lack of confidence, insufficient knowledge or skills, inadequate review of the lessons, and time constraints during exams also contribute to cheating behaviors, as approximately 40% of students reported. Interestingly, only between 20-30% of these students blamed the engagement in cheating attributed to their teachers' faults and high score commitment. Again, gender and employment characteristics appear to be no different.

School factors

Table 4 indicates that exam pressure emerged as a major influence. Around half of the university students reported the difficulty of their university exam papers as a key reason for cheating. This perception by gender and employment status seemed to be no different. The emphasis placed by schools on grades rather than actual learning was another common concern, identified by roughly 40% of the participants, with no notable difference between gender and employment status. In addition, only about 30% of the students admitted that the low risk of being caught during exams and large class sizes where student-teacher interaction may be reduced motivated their dishonest behavior. This has no variation by gender and employment status.

Social factors

According to Table 5, peer pressure, parental pressure, and the normalization of cheating appeared to contribute to academic dishonest behaviors, to some extent. Around 30% of the university students admitted to cheating because they learned the behavior from their peers. Similarly, the participants identified the social normalization of cheating and parental expectations as reasons to cheat, as approximately 30% of students reported. These findings are consistent across gender and employment status.

Technological factors

The findings demonstrate that technology might facilitate academic cheating, with no distinct patterns across gender and employment status (See Table 6). Digital collaboration was common since about 40% of university students reported that they may have engaged in cheating due to the use of applications like Zoom or Discord to share answers. Similarly, electronic devices and search engines were also used resource during exams, identified by around 40% of students. Interestingly, using social media platforms like Facebook were mentioned less as a source of cheating, with only between 20% and 30% of the participants reported. Again, there appears to be no noticeable difference by gender and employment status.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal that academic cheating is a relatively common behavior among university students in Phnom Penh, Cambodia. The research found that almost half of the students were involved in academic dishonesty, especially on an occasional basis. This aligns with other previous studies (Anitha & Sundaram, 2021; Bloomfield et al., 2021; Whitley 1998). The results reflect the pervasiveness of normalization of cheating within the academic environment. Similarly, the present study confirms that cheating is not a rare or isolated act but rather a commonly observed behavior in Cambodian classrooms.

Beyond the prevalence, the findings of this research also illustrate the multifaceted nature of academic cheating among university students in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, which points out

the interplay of personal, school, social, and technological factors. Such findings are consistent with and add to previous literature, especially in areas of research in Cambodia. Fear of failure and poor understanding of course content emerged as the most prominent reasons for academic dishonesty. It concurs with previous literature (Woods, 1957; Yu et al., 2016), which indicates that students turn to cheating as a coping mechanism to overcome academic anxiety and their knowledge gaps. The fear of failure is well internalized by students, irrespective of their gender or employment status. This suggests that performance anxiety is experienced among students. These psychological stressors are exacerbated by a lack of skills or knowledge, review of the lessons, confidence, and time management. This means that students may have engaged in academic cheating due to a lack of preparedness to meet academic expectations. The individual pressure may be intensified by the difficulty of exam papers and the institutional priority on grades over actual learning were serious sources of cheating, which can imply that universities in Cambodia may unintentionally encourage cheating as they focus too much on exams rather than helping students truly understand the lessons.

These results are consistent with the assertions that performance-based settings reinforce the level of dishonesties (Anderman & Midgley, 2004; Anderman & Koenka, 2017). Peer influence, parental pressure and the normalization of cheating behaviors further contributed to university students' academic dishonesty. These results concur with those of the previous studies (McCabe et al., 2008; Rettinger & Kramer, 2008), which pointed out to the importance of the power of social norms as a determinant of academic cheating. The findings indicate that in the Cambodian classroom, cheating might be more of a learned behavior rather than an impulsive decision. Besides, a cultural pressure to succeed and achieve honor may drive students to engage in unethical behaviors with a view to not disappointing their families. These factors may be intertwined with technological factors with the rise of digital tools as new ways to cheat. The results strengthen the prior study of King and Case (2014) regarding the emergence of the phenomenon of e-cheating. This suggests that this type of behavior is also widespread, regardless of gender or employment status, meaning that the normalization of digital cheating is taking place among students.

This study has implications for universities and education policymakers in Cambodia. Institutions are advised to formulate and apply a comprehensive policy on academic integrity and carry out regular awareness programs, as well as invest in helping faculty members to identify and respond to academic dishonesty. Academic integrity should be enhanced by focusing on improved time management, study skills, and academic supports. Thus, universities should establish peer mentoring programs and workshops on study skills and stress management. Furthermore, universities should apply strict examination regulations, such as prohibiting phones and electronic devices during exams and administering multiple versions of exams. However, despite this contribution, we also acknowledge the limitations of the study's generalizability,

considering its adaptation of non-probability sampling methods and small sample size.

Ethical approval: This research included human participants, and the data were collected with their consent.

Availability of data: The data are available upon request.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in this study.

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